

Supporting Information

Electronic structure and stability of the active surface phase of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ spinel alkaline O_2 evolution electrocatalysts: from an epitaxial model catalyst perspective

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Figure S1. XRD results of pristine Co_3O_4 (black), $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ (red) and NiCo_2O_4 (blue).

Figure S2. XRR test results (black curves) and the corresponding fitted results (red curves). (a) pristine Co_3O_4 , (b) pristine $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$, (c) pristine NiCo_2O_4 , (d) Co_3O_4 after 30 CV, (e) $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ after 30 CV and (f) NiCo_2O_4 after 30 CV. The XRR results of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 1.0$) are fitted by XRR fitting software ANALYSE from Rayflex.

Table S1. Roughness obtained by XRR, SE and AFM

Roughness obtained by different methods (nm)			
Sample	XRR	SE	AFM
Co ₃ O ₄ pristine	0.9 ± 0.13	1.12 ± 0.16	0.7 ± 0.1
Co ₃ O ₄ after 30 CV	1.1 ± 0.12	4.05 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.2
Ni _{0.3} Co _{2.7} O ₄ pristine	0.6 ± 0.12	0.72 ± 0.22	0.8 ± 0.1
Ni _{0.3} Co _{2.7} O ₄ after 30 CV	0.8 ± 0.09	1.20 ± 0.26	1.3 ± 0.3
NiCo ₂ O ₄ pristine	1.1 ± 0.04	3.20 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.2
NiCo ₂ O ₄ after 30 CV	0.6 ± 0.08	1.17 ± 0.02	0.4 ± 0.1

Figure S3. AFM 3D images of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ thin films in pristine state and after 30 CV cycles. (a) Co_3O_4 pristine, (b) Co_3O_4 after 30 CV, (c) $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$, pristine, (d) $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$, after 30 CV, (e) NiCo_2O_4 pristine and (f) NiCo_2O_4 after 30 CV.

Figure S4. Experimental (dashed lines) and modeled (solid lines) spectroscopic ellipsometry data in terms of the pseudo-dielectric function for $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ and NiCo_2O_4 . (a) $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ pristine sample, (b) $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ after 30 CV, (c) NiCo_2O_4 pristine sample and (d) NiCo_2O_4 after 30 CV.

Figure S5. $\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{2.7}\text{O}_4$ SXPS of (a) Co 2p, (b) O 1s and (c) VB spectra after different CV cycles; (d) shifts of core level binding energies (BE) and Fermi level (E_F) position relative to the VBM deduced from the change of Co 2p, O 1s and VBM BE as a function of CV cycles.

Figure S6. NiCo₂O₄ SXPS of (a) Co 2p, (b) O 1s and (c) VB spectra after different CV cycles; (d) shifts of core level binding energies (BE) and Fermi level (E_F) position relative to the VBM deduced from the change of Co 2p, O 1s and VBM BE as a function of CV cycles.

Figure S7. Co₃O₄ NEXAFS spectra of (a) O-K edge and (b) Co L-edge after different CV cycles.

Figure S8. The percentage content of the hole state of Ni_{0.3}Co_{2.7}O₄ (black) and NiCo₂O₄ (red) with different CV cycles, calculated from O K-edge spectra by the integrated peak area of the hole state at 529 eV divided by the total areas of peaks at 529 eV and 530.5 eV.

Figure S9. CV polarization curves with different CV cycles. (a) Co₃O₄ and (b) Ni_{0.3}Co_{2.7}O₄.